

FURTHER STUDIES ON THE HYDROLYSIS OF STARCH BY SWEET POTATO AMYLASE.

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The nature of the hydrolysis of amyloamylose and soluble starch by sweet potato amylase and β -amylase of barley is investigated. The sweet potato amylase behaves like a pure β -amylase. The amylase selectively hydrolyses a portion of the starch substance, leaving a residual material which resembles erythrogranulose. Amyloamylose is hydrolysed completely by both the enzymes, without noteworthy inhibition, and the colour with iodine remains unchanged until almost complete saccharification takes place. During the saccharification of amyloamylose by sweet potato amylase the intensity of the blue colour with iodine diminishes. The residual material is hydrolysed by α -amylase from barley, but it remains unaffected by sweet potato amylase.

It would appear from the study of starch chemistry that the only line of enquiry which promises to be of immense value in the elucidation of the structure of starch is the study of its hydrolysis by the enzyme diastase. In fact the greater part of the knowledge we possess of starch has been derived from a study of its hydrolytic products under the influence of enzymes. The importance of such studies lies not only in the elucidation of the structure of starch but also in the solution of the problem of enzymes and their reactions in general.

In more recent times fresh light has been thrown on the enquiry by a study of the action of different types of amylases on starch. As a result of such studies, investigators have put forward different views on the amyolytic decomposition of starch.

The Theory of Specificity.

Kuhn (*Annalen*, 1925, 443, 1) has made the discovery that there are two different types of amylases which are separable under certain conditions. One of these amylases converts starch into α -maltose, the other produces only β -maltose under similar conditions. These observations indicate two possibilities—either (i) there are two distinct starches made up of α - and β -maltose units respectively or (ii) both the α - and β - forms of glucosidic linkage exist in the starch molecule, either alternately or according to some regular plan so that the starch molecule, when hydrolysed, breaks down at the one or the other centre. It is, however, considered that the two forms of maltose arise from the breakdown of a single substrate through alternative types of hydrolysis.

α - and β -Starches.

The existence of two different specific amylases is a strong point in favour of the existence of correspondingly different components in starch molecule. More recently Van Klinkenberg (*Proc. Acad. Sci. Amsterdam*, 1931, **34**, 893; *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1932, **209**, 253; *ibid.*, 1932, **212**, 173; *Ergebnisse Enzymforsch.*, 1934, **3**, 73) has put forward the view that the liberation of α - and β -maltose by α - and β -malt amylase is due, not to alternative types of hydrolysis of a single substrate, but to the selective hydrolysis of two components of starch, which he designated as α - and β -starch. The following scheme represents the view of Van Klinkenberg on the relations between the two starches and the two amylases.

The hypothesis developed by Van Klinkenberg is based on the following points :

(1) When soluble starch is hydrolysed to completion by β -amylase, the reducing power of the products corresponds to 64% of the theoretical maltose. The iodine colour remains blue or blue-violet owing to the presence of non-reducing residual material. This residual fraction resembles Wijsman's "erythrogranulose" or Baker's " α -amylodextrin" (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, **81**, 1177) This fraction is designated as α -starch and constitutes about 36% of the starch.

(2) When soluble starch is hydrolysed by α -amylase the reducing power rises rapidly to a value that corresponds to 36% of the theoretical maltose, after which it continues to rise slowly. The initial rapid rise is interpreted as being due to the selective hydrolysis of α -starch (36% of the total substrate) to maltose. The slow hydrolysis beyond 36% in presence of α -amylase was explained by the supposed slow transformation of β - into α -starch. The converse transformation (α -starch into β -starch) does not occur because a sharp "saccharification limit is always observed in the hydrolysis of starch by β -amylase.

Hanes (*Canadian J. Res.*, 1935, **13B**, 185) by carefully planned experiments has confirmed in essential respects the observation of Van Klinkenberg concerning the action of α - and β -malt amylases. But he has considerably modified the view of Van Klinkenberg by studying the reducing products with the help of yeast for their fractionation. The experiments of Hanes have shown that α -amylase does not selectively hydrolyse the erythrogranulose

fraction of starch, but that from the beginning of the reaction the greater part of reducing material arises from the β -starch fraction. The recent findings of Freeman and Hopkins (*Biochem. J.*, 1936, 30, 446) also do not support the view of Van Klinkenberg of selective hydrolysis of different components of the starch by the respective amylases. The conclusions drawn from their experiments are as follows.

(1) "Both α - and β -amylases readily attack and hydrolyse completely the amyloamylose component (about 20%) of starch, and a portion of the erythroamylose component. (2) Both enzymes hydrolyse much the same fraction, 60% of the starch; but whereas the remainder (α -amyloextrin) is almost, if not completely, resistant to the β -amylase, it can be with difficulty hydrolysed by the α -enzyme. (3) α -Amyloextrin, the hydrolysis of which has been commenced by the α -amylase, can be further degraded to a certain extent by the β -amylase. The α -enzyme holds the key to further hydrolysis. (4) In degrading starch to the 50% stage, the α -enzyme does so mainly at the expense of the portion which is other than amyloextrin, since action on the residue by β -amylase still leaves about 30% of the original starch unattacked."

Amyloamylose and Erythro amyloses.

According to Samec and Mayer (*Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1921, 31, 272) starch in solution contains certain distinct components which may be fractionated by electrodialysis yielding respectively amyloamylose (blue with iodine) and erythroamylose (red with iodine). Samec and Waldschmidt-Leitz (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1931, 203, 16) have further investigated the hydrolysis of these components by different amylases, and have shown that amyloamylose is hydrolysed by pancreatic (α -), barley (β -) and unfractionated malt (mixture $\alpha + \beta$) amylases relatively easily and completely, but erythrogranulose only with difficulty. Thus Van Klinkenberg's so-called α - and β -starches are not identical with amylo- and erythro-amyloses, though they might represent fractions of the erythroamylose, which constitutes at least 60% (according to Freeman and Hopkins, *loc. cit.*) to 83% (according to Samec) of the total starch.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to elucidating certain aspects of the amylolytic decomposition of starch by sweet potato amylase, and with the primary object of obtaining evidence as to the nature of the amylase.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Substrates.—Zulkowsky's soluble starch was used. *Amyloamylose* was prepared by electrodialysis of 2% potato starch, autoclaved at 120° for

$\frac{1}{2}$ hour at 220 volt using platinum electrodes and cellophanè as the dialysing membrane (Samiec and Mayer, *loc. cit.*).

Preparation of Amylases.

Sweet Potato Amylase.—The amylase was prepared from the tuber by the method previously described (Giri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 339) by precipitation from the aqueous extract of the malt with alcohol. Control experiments under the condition of reaction employed in the experiments indicated the absence of any maltase activity from the amylase preparations.

β -Amylase from Barley.—The enzyme was prepared from ungerminated barley by the method described by Hanes (*loc. cit.*). Ungerminated barley was ground to a fine flour. 200 G. of the flour were extracted with 700 c.c. of 50% alcohol for 2 hours with occasional shaking and centrifuged. The residue was again re-extracted with 700 c.c. of 50% alcohol for 2 hours and centrifuged. The supernatant liquors were combined and after filtration the enzyme was precipitated by adding alcohol to a concentration of 80%. The precipitate was removed by centrifuging, washed with alcohol and ether and finally dried in a desiccator.

α -Amylase from Barley-malt.—Barley seeds were soaked in flowing water for 24 hours and allowed to germinate at 25-28° for 3 days. The seedlings were then dried in the sun and ground to a flour. The preparation of α -amylase from the malt thus obtained was exactly similar to that described by Hanes (*loc. cit.*). 250 G. of the flour were extracted once with 700 c.c. of dilute aqueous solution of potassium hydrogen phosphate solution (0.05%) for 2 hours at about 4-5° and again with 500 c.c. of the phosphate solution for about $\frac{1}{2}$ an hour. The extracts were mixed together and centrifuged to remove any suspended material. Alcohol was then added to the combined extract to a final concentration of 60%. The precipitate was dispersed in 350 c.c. of water and heated to 70° for 15 minutes in order to destroy the activity of β -amylase. After cooling it was centrifuged and filtered. The enzyme was again precipitated by adding alcohol to give a concentration of 65%. The precipitate was washed with 90% alcohol and finally with absolute alcohol and dried in *vacuo* over calcium chloride. The yield was about 0.7 g.

The purity of the preparations of α - and β -amylases as prepared by the above methods was tested by the diffusion method described by Giri (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1934, 17A, 127). The results showed that the preparations behaved like pure α - and β -amylases.

The maltose was determined by the method of Willstätter and Schüdel (*Ber.*, 1918, 51, 780).

1 c.c. $N/10-I_2 = 17.15$ mg. of maltose.

The percentage of hydrolysis is expressed as percentage of maltose (105.5%) theoretically equivalent to the complete conversion of the quantity of substrate used.

The " Saccharification limit " for the Hydrolysis of Starch by Sweet Potato Amylase and Barley β -Amylase.

It is well known that when starch is decomposed by amylases inhibition zones and saccharification limits are formed, which are found to vary with different types of amylases, and the results obtained by several workers are found to be of varying magnitude. The following table represents the values given by several workers.

Authors.	Reference.	Inhibition zones.
	<i>α-Amylase.</i>	
Syniewski	... <i>Annalen</i> , 1925, 241 , 288.	about 34%
Polak and Tychowski	... <i>Biochem. Z.</i> , 1929, 214 , 216.	" 36%
Van Klinkenberg	... <i>Z. physiol. Chem.</i> , 1932, 209 , 253.	" 36%
Hanes	... <i>Canadian J. Res.</i> , 1935, 13B , 185.	" 34-38%
Blom, Bak and Braae	... <i>Z. physiol. Chem.</i> , 1936, 241 , 273.	" 33-40%
	<i>β-Amylase.</i>	<i>Saccharification limits.</i>
Baker	... <i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1902, 81 , 1177.	60-65%
Ling and Nanji	... <i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1923, 123 , 2666; 1925, 127 , 636.	67%
Polak and Tychowski	... <i>loc. cit.</i>	66%
Van Klinkenberg	... <i>loc. cit.</i>	64%
Hopkins, Cope and Green...	<i>J. Inst. of Brew.</i> , 1933, 39 , 487.	64-65%
Hanes	... <i>loc. cit.</i>	62%
Blom, Bak and Braae	... <i>loc. cit.</i>	53.1 $\pm$ 0.5%

The figures in the above table indicate that the hydrolysis limit of the decomposition of starch is reached at 60-67% of hydrolysis of starch. The amylase of resting barley grain is almost pure β -amylase, but a small amount of α -amylase is present in the crude aqueous extracts. In the following experiments the action of β -amylase of barley, prepared according to the method of Hanes on starch was studied and compared with that of the amylase from sweet potato.

All reactions were performed at p_H 4.6 (0.0286*N*-acetate buffer) and p_H 6.0 (0.0286*N*-acetate buffer) for barley and sweet potato amylase activities respectively, the enzyme solutions having been brought to p_H 4.6 and 6.0 by the addition of acetate buffer. The total volume of the reaction mixture amounted to 140 c.c. and the amount of starch present in the reaction mixture was 1750 mg. The progress of hydrolysis was followed by measuring the amount of maltose formed at known intervals of time, controls for the reducing power of the enzyme preparation and of all substrates being deducted. Usually the maltose determinations were carried out on 20 c.c. samples.

Curves 1-4 refer respectively to S. P. amylase (digest No. III), barley β -amylase (digest No. IV), S. P. amylase (digest No. II) and S. P. amylase (digest No. I).

All results are expressed as percentage of maltose (105.5%) theoretically equivalent to the complete conversion of the quantity of substrate used. The results are shown in Table I and in Fig. 1.

The figures in Table I indicate that a sharp saccharification limit is reached at 61% conversion. This value appears to be independent of the concentration of the enzyme. Further the data show that there is close agreement between the two figures obtained for the saccharification limits by the β -amylase from barley and sweet potato amylase. Further it is seen from Fig. 1 that the hydrolysis is considerably lowered when about 50% saccharification is reached. This experiment would indicate that the sweet potato amylase is a pure β -amylase.

TABLE I.

Saccharification limits for the hydrolysis of starch by sweet potato amylase and barley β -amylase.

Time.	Hydrolysis as percentage theoretical maltose.			
	S. P. amylase digest No. I = 5 c.c. of 0.1%.	S. P. amylase digest No. II = 10 c.c. of 1%.	S. P. amylase digest No. III. = 20 c.c. of 1%.	Barley β -amylase digest No. IV. = 10 c.c. of 0.5%.
1 hr.	24.4	38.1	49.0	44.6
2	39.7	51.4	54.2	53.3
4	51.4	55.2	58.0	55.2
6	52.7	55.3	59.2	55.3
9	54.0	56.6	60.0	56.6
24	56.0	58.4	60.4	58.4
48	57.2	60.5	60.6	60.6
72	58.5	60.6	60.6	60.7

Hydrolysis of Amyloamylose by Sweet Potato Amylase and Barley β -Amylase.

One of the striking characteristic properties of pure β -amylase is that it hydrolyses amyloamylose in such a way that the iodine colour remains blue until about 90% of maltose is formed, then it becomes violet and finally rose (Samec and Waldschmidt-Leitz, *loc. cit.*, Samec, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1935, 236, 103). With a view to finding out whether sweet potato amylase behaves like a pure β -amylase in its action on amyloamylose, the following experiment was conducted.

The hydrolysis of amyloamylose was followed in two digests with sweet potato amylase and barley β -amylase.

Each digest consisted of 250 mg. of amyloamylose, 20 c.c. of $M/5$ acetic acid—acetate buffer (adjusted to p_H 6.0 and p_H 5.2 respectively for sweet potato and barley β -amylase), and 5 c.c. of enzyme extract (0.1% S. P.-amylase and 0.5% barley- β -amylase) in a total volume of 125 c.c. The mixtures were incubated at 35° and the maltose was determined in

10 c.c. samples at frequent intervals. The colouration with iodine was noted by adding 1 c.c. of reaction mixture to 1 c.c. of $N/100$ -iodine solution. The results are shown in Table II and Fig. 2.

Curves A and B refer respectively to barley- β -amylase and S. P. amylase.

TABLE II.

Saccharification and iodine colouration.

Amyloamylose = 0.25 g. 0.2N-Acetic acid—acetate buffer = 20 c.c.
Total volume = 125 c.c. Temp. = 35°

Sweet potato amylase			Barley - β -amylase		
Time	Saccharification in % maltose.	Colour with I_2 .	Time.	Saccharification in % maltose.	colour with I_2 .
10 min	4.3	Blue	10 min	22	Blue
20	8.5	„	20	43	„
60	30	„	40	64	„
90	43	„	60	78	„
150	52	„	90	86	„
210	64	„	150	87	„
300	78	„	300	90	Bluish-green
1440	99.1	Violet	1440	95.2	Violet

It is clear from the results of this experiment that the action of sweet potato amylase on amyloamylose is very similar to that of β -amylase of barley. This experiment in conjunction with the value obtained for the saccharification limit, thus gives ground for the statement that sweet potato amylase is a pure β -amylase. Further the results would indicate that amyloamylose undergoes saccharification to theoretical completion without noteworthy inhibition.

Changes in the Iodine Colouration during the Hydrolysis of Amyloamylose by Sweet Potato Amylase.

In a previous communication (Giri, *Science*, 1935, 81, 343) it was

○—○ ... 0 hr.
 ●—● ... 1 hr.—16.79% maltose
 ▲—▲ ... 5 hr.—86% "

reported that the colour reactions produced with iodine by different starches in the course of hydrolysis differ markedly with the kind of starch and also with the concentration of iodine used. This may possibly be due to the presence of amylo- and erythroamyloses, the two most important components of the starch, in various starches in different proportions. With a view to throw more light on the behaviour of the starches in the course of hydrolysis towards iodine, the following experiment was carried out with amyloamylose which can be considered as a uniform substrate unlike starch which is a heterogeneous substrate, in the sense that it contains number of components which differ in their behaviour towards iodine. In a recent communication Samec (*loc. cit.*) has also shown that the behaviour of starch substance towards iodine changes during amylolysis in different ways. It changes (1) the colour tone and (2) the colour intensity. He has shown that the hydrolysis of amyloamylose with β -diastase from barley does not bring about any definite change in the iodine colour even when after high saccharification (90% maltose) stage is reached. The blue forming function of starch, however, goes on diminishing in the course of hydrolysis, and for the attainment of maximum colour, smaller quantities of iodine are required, with the increase in saccharification.

The following experiment was carried out for the purpose of determining whether sweet potato amylase behaves in a like manner in the hydrolysis of amyloamylose. The change in the colour intensity with iodine in the course of hydrolysis of amyloamylose by sweet potato amylase was determined as outlined below.

The reaction mixture (total volume 180 c.c.) consisted of 20 c.c. of $M/5$, acetate buffer at pH 5.5; 150 c.c. of substrate containing 495 mg. of amyloamylose, and 10 c.c. of 0.1% sweet potato amylase. Two sets of such digests were prepared. The digests were incubated at 35° . At known intervals of time, 40 c.c. of the reaction mixture were removed. A series of 50 c.c. flasks containing known amounts of $N/200-I_2$ solution and diluted with water was arranged. As soon as the aliquot (40 c.c.) from the reaction mixture was removed, 5 c.c. of the mixture were added into each flask, made up to the mark with water and the colour was compared in a colorimeter against a standard. The readings thus obtained were recorded. Simultaneously the percentage of maltose formed was also determined.

Standard for Colorimetry.—5 C.c. of the original amyloamylose solution (containing 330 mg. in 100 c.c.) were added into a 50 c.c. flask which contained 1 c.c. of $N/200-I_2$, diluted with water, and made up to 50 c.c. This was used as standard.

The results are presented in Table IIIA and graphically in Fig. 3, in which the quantity of iodine added is expressed along the abscissa and the thickness of the iodine-starch solution (in the present case the direct colorimetric scale reading) as ordinate. In Table III B are given the percentage of maltose formed in the same reaction mixture at known time intervals.

TABLE IIIA.

Variation in the intensity of the blue colour obtained with iodine during the hydrolysis of amyloamylose by sweet potato amylase.

No.	$N/200-I_2$ added.	Colorimetric reading against the standard after hydrolysis.			
		0 hour.	1 hour.	3½ hours.	5 hours.
1	0.3 c.c.	64	60	70	Colourless
2	0.5	25	25	27	40
3	1.0	10	9.8	10.3	24
4	1.5	5.3	5.9	6.0	13
5	2.0	4.2	4.2	4.3	12.3
6	3.0	2.6	2.8	3.0	11.8

TABLE IIIB.

Percentage of theoretical maltose (105.5 %) formed in the hydrolysis of amyloamylose by sweet potato amylase.

Time.	Maltose formed in the total vol. of reaction mixture.	Colour with 1 c.c. of N/200-I ₂ .
1 hr.	16.7%	Blue
3½	60	Blue
5	86	Blue
20	88	Blue
44	96	Violet

It will be seen that the property of the starch responsible for the formation of blue colour with iodine diminishes with the increase in saccharification. Further the concentration of iodine required to attain the maximum colour also diminishes with increase in saccharification. The results obtained with sweet potato amylase are thus in agreement with those of Samec in regard to the general behaviour of β -amylase on amyloamylose.

On the Residual Material Resulting from the Hydrolysis of Starch by Sweet Potato Amylase.

Previous workers (Van Klinkenberg, Hanes and others) have shown that when β -amylase acts on starch, the hydrolysis does not go to completion. A fraction resembling Wijsman's erythrogranulose, or Baker's α -amyloxytrin, which is designated as α -starch by Van Klinkenberg and which constitutes about 36 % of the starch, is left behind unattacked. According to Van Klinkenberg this residual material does not possess any reducing action and it gives a purple or blue colour with iodine. β -Amylases are considered to be specific for β -starch which constitutes about 64 % of the starch. Erythrogranulose is not attacked by β -amylase. But on prolonged treatment with large amounts of β -amylase, traces of reducing material are formed, and the iodine colour remains unchanged. It is readily hydrolysed by α -amylase with the production of reducing material, and the iodine colouration undergoes a sequence of changes from blue-violet through rose and brown and leading finally to complete absence of colouration.

In the following experiment the preparation and properties of the residual material left after the hydrolysis of starch by sweet potato amylase is reported.

The Preparation of the Residual Material from Soluble Starch by Sweet Potato Amylase Hydrolysis.

The digestion mixture contained 500 c.c. of 9% starch, 50 c.c. of acetate buffer ($N/5$) of p_H 5.5 and 50 c.c. of 0.1% sweet potato amylase solution. After 48 hours' digestion at 37° the mixture gave violet colour with iodine. On boiling the digestion mixture, the slight turbidity disappeared and it became transparent. After cooling the mixture gave blue colour with iodine, thereby indicating that the groups responsible for the production of blue colour with iodine are liberated on boiling. 20 C.c. more of the enzyme solution were again added to the digest and incubated at 37° for 24 hours. The reaction with iodine was again tested and it was found that it gave a violet colour with iodine. Once again 20 c.c. more of the enzyme were added and digested for 48 hours, the total period of digestion amounting to 120 hours. At the end of this period the digestion mixture was boiled to destroy the enzyme and after cooling the colour with iodine was tested and found to give violet-red colour. The reducing power determined on 1 c.c. samples was about 60% of the theoretical maltose.

The residual material from the digestion mixture was precipitated by the addition of 1500 c.c. of 95% alcohol to 550 c.c. of the digestion mixture. The precipitate was allowed to settle by keeping it at laboratory temperature for about 4 hours. The top layer of liquid was decanted. The residual mass formed at the bottom of the beaker was washed with 70% alcohol and then with absolute alcohol and filtered through a Buchner funnel. It was then washed with ether and kept for drying in a desiccator. The residual material thus obtained was slightly gummy and transparent in appearance. For further examination the solution of the residual material in water was used.

TABLE IV.

Hydrolysis of the residual material by sweet potato amylase and α -amylase of barley malt.

Digest No. I	25 C.c. of the residual material containing 325 mg. of the substance. 20 C.c. of acetate buffer of p_H 5.5. 10 C.c. of 0.1% sweet potato amylase. 25 C.c. of water.
Digest No. II	25 C.c. of the residual material. 20 C.c. of acetate buffer $N/5$ of p_H 5.2. 1 C.c. of 0.5% α -amylase from barley malt. 24 C.c. of water.
Digest No. III	Same as digest No. II except that 2 c.c. of the α -amylase were added.

The total volume of all the digests was adjusted to 80 c.c. and digested at 35°. 10 C.c. of the digests were removed at stated intervals and the reducing power was determined. Simultaneously the colouration with iodine was also determined. The results are presented in Table V and Fig. 4.

It will be seen that α -amylase does not completely hydrolyse the residual fraction. The results show that it is hydrolysed to less than 50% of the theoretical amount of maltose. On the other hand the residual material is hydrolysed with great difficulty by sweet potato amylase.

FIG. 4.

Curves 1 and 2 refer respectively to 2 c.c. and 1 c.c. of α -amylase.

TABLE V.

Hydrolysis of the residual material by sweet potato amylase and α -amylase of barley malt.

Time.	Sweet potato amylase.		α -Amylase from barley malt.			
	Digest No. I.		Digest No. II.		Digest No. III.	
	Reducing power as theoretical maltose.	Colour with I ₂ .	Reducing power as theoretical maltose.	Colour with I ₂ .	Reducing power as theoretical maltose.	Colour with I ₂ .
15 min.	0	Violet-red	6'1	Red	11	Colourless.
30	0	"	10'2	Colourless	17'1	"
60	0	"	14'0	"	20'2	"
1080	7'2	"	28'0	"	34'1	"
2520	10'2	Red	44'0	"	46'6	"

In the case of α -amylase the iodine colouration disappears when less than 10% of maltose are formed in the digest.

D I S C U S S I O N.

The present study has thrown light on the nature of sweet potato amylase and the constitution of starch. In previous communications, it was shown that the enzyme behaves like pure β -amylase. The present investigation has further strengthened this view. Thus the saccharification limit for the hydrolysis of starch by sweet potato amylase corresponds to the value obtained with β -amylase of barley. Further the nature of its hydrolysis of amyloamylose is characteristic of pure β -amylase.

The residual material obtained after the hydrolysis of starch by sweet potato amylase appears to resemble the crythrogranulose fraction of starch in its hydrolysis by α - and β -amylases.

According to Van Klinkenberg the starch is composed of two components, the one (α -starch = 36% of total quantity) producing colour with iodine, and the other (β -starch = 64%) which does not give any colour with iodine. By the hydrolysis with α -amylase, the α -starch is hydrolysed, and the β -starch is transformed into α -form, which is further hydrolysed by the enzyme. In this manner the iodine reaction disappears before the saccharification is complete. The conversion into β -starch is, however, very difficult, and hence the limit of β -amylase hydrolysis has been found to occur when 64% of saccharification has taken place. Thus according to Van Klinkenberg the iodine colouring atomic groups are present in α -starch only and the iodine reaction, therefore, only disappears by the action of α -amylase. The experiments described in the present paper appear to render this view untenable. It was observed that the blue colour obtained with iodine by amyloamylose diminishes during hydrolysis by β -amylase from sweet potato. Therefore β -starch also should possess groups which produce colour with iodine.

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